

supplied as Fe EDTA in amounts required for Fe concentrations of 0.09, 0.89, and 1.78 mM. Nutrient solutions were changed weekly. Solution pH was adjusted to 4 ± 0.2 initially, then once every 2 d with 0.1 N NaOH or 0.1 N HCl.

Seeds of rice cultivars were germinated in nutrient solution using 2-liter plastic pots. At 17 d, uniform seedlings were transplanted to acrylic discs with holes in the center and held in place with cotton. Discs were transferred to plastic pots containing about 8 liters nutrient solution with different Fe treatments. Each treatment was replicated twice.

After 35 d growth in Fe-treated solutions, plant shoots and roots were harvested separately and washed in distilled water. Plant material was dried at about 80 °C to a constant weight. Dry matter was ground and digested with a 2:1 mixture of nitric and perchloric acids. Composite samples of 12 rice cultivars per treatment were analyzed chemically for N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Zn, Cu, Mn, and Fe. The P concentration in the digest was determined colorimetrically; other elements were determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy. Total N in the tissue was determined using a Tecator 1016 digester and 1004 distilling unit.

In general, uptake of all nutrients was reduced with increasing Fe concentration in the growth medium (Table 1). Among macronutrients, P uptake was most highly affected, followed by K and N. Among micronutrients, absorption of Mn and Zn was most affected. Nutrient inhibition by Fe can be put in the following order (Table 2):

macronutrients — P>K>N>Mg>Ca
micronutrients — Mn>Zn>Cu.

Among macronutrients, P uptake was highly inhibited and Ca uptake was least affected. Among micronutrients, Mn was most inhibited and Cu least affected. The results suggest that with higher Fe concentrations in lowland rice, P, K, and Zn deficiencies will be the first to appear. Fe toxicity problem in lowland rice could be alleviated by increased P, K, and Zn fertilization. □

Table 2. Inhibition of nutrient uptake by higher concentrations of Fe in rice cultivars shoots

Nutrient	Cultivars (no.) under each group					
	Fe 0.89 mM			Fe 1.78 mM		
	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
N	—	6	6	—	7	5
P	—	—	12	—	—	12
K	—	1	11	—	1	11
Ca	2	10	—	2	10	—
Mg	—	8	4	—	8	4
Zn	—	5	7	1	3	8
Cu	1	10	1	1	8	3
Mn	—	1	11	—	4	8

$$\text{Inhibition} = \frac{\text{nutrient content at optimum Fe level} - \text{nutrient content at high Fe levels}}{\text{nutrient content at optimum Fe level}} \times 100$$

Optimum Fe level was 0.09 mM.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of integrated nitrogen management in rice on soil organic carbon and on succeeding wheat crop yield

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We studied the residual effect of applied N (organic + inorganic) in lowland rice on soil organic C content and grain yield of the succeeding wheat crop grown without fertilizer on a Mollisol of the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh.

The silty clay loam soil had pH 7.2, 1.20% organic C, 0.116% total N, 42.5 kg available P/ha, 214 kg available K/ha, and bulk density 1.33 g/cc. Soil

Soil organic C after wet season rice harvest and wheat yield after integrated N management in rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1984-85 and 1985-86.

Treatment ^b	N (kg/ha)	Soil organic C (%) after wet season rice harvest		Wheat grain yield (t/ha)	
		1984-85	1985-86	1984-85	1985-86
No N	0	1.16	1.16 a	1.0 c	1.3 c
USG	58	1.17	1.17 a	1.2 b	1.9 b
USG + fresh wheat straw (29+29)	58	1.17	1.21 ab	1.2 b	2.2 b
PU + azolla (58+29)	87	1.20	1.20 ab	1.3 ab	1.9 b
PU + fresh wheat straw (58+29)	87	1.19	1.24 abc	1.3 ab	2.1 b
USG + azolla (58+29)	87	1.24	1.25 abc	1.4 a	2.0 b
USG + fresh wheat straw (58+29)	87	1.19	1.29 bc	1.3 ab	3.3 a
PU	120	1.17	1.20 ab	1.3 ab	1.9 b
USG + azolla ^c (60+60)	120	1.26	1.31 c	1.6 a	3.5 a
CD (0.05)		—	0.09	0.11	0.45

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly. ^bFigures in parentheses are kg N/ha. Treatment of rice crop only in both years. Azolla was incorporated. Prilled urea (PU) was best split. USG placed 10-12 cm deep 7 d after planting rice. Fresh wheat straw incorporated at puddling. In the first year, azolla with PU or USG showed more increase in organic C content. Azolla left on the surface at incorporation multiplied and added organic matter throughout rice growth. In other treatments, variations were 0.01-0.03%. ^cHalf the azolla N incorporated at planting and half inoculated 7 d after planting rice.

organic C (by modified Walkley and Black method) after harvesting the wet season rice crop and wheat grain yield were observed 1984-85 and 1985-86.

Integrated use of organic and inorganic fertilizer in rice had a significant residual effect on the succeeding wheat crop grain yield (see

table). The residual effect was more pronounced the second year. In both years, urea supergranule (USG) (60 kg N) + azolla (60 kg N) applied to the rice crop showed the maximum residual effect on wheat yield (0.6 t/ha in 1984-85, 2.2 t/ha in 1985-86). Fresh wheat straw combined with chemical N in rice

showed a higher residual effect the second year. Chemical N alone had very low residual effect. The increase in grain yield of wheat after organic-inorganic N fertilization in rice is explained by the significant modification of organic C, which in turn gives more hydrolyzable organic N. □

Disease management

Ovewintering of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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We studied the overwintering of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* — the causal pathogen of bacterial blight (BB) — in soil, seeds, and infected leaves collected from a rice crop artificially inoculated during the 1985-86 crop season.

Samples of seeds and leaves were collected in cloth bags and stored in a refrigerator (8±1 °C), incubator (28±1°C), and at room temperature (5-42°C) in the laboratory. Bacterium in the samples was measured at 1-mo intervals from Nov 1985 to Aug 1986. Methods were direct plating (DP), dilution streak plating (DSP), ooze test (OT), pathological test (PT) with

Recovery^a of *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* from soil, seed, and leaves collected from diseased fields showing heavy infection with BB during the 1984-85 crop season, Hisar, India.

Source of infection	Storage conditions	Detection methods	Recovery										
			Nov 1985	Dec 1985	Jan 1986	Feb 1986	Mar 1986	Apr 1986	May 1986	Jun 1986	Jul 1986	Aug 1986	
Soil		DP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		DSP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		IF-S	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Seed	Refrigerator (8±1°C)	DP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		DSP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		IF-S	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		GOB	ND	-	-								
		PT	ND	ND									
	Incubator (28±1°C)	DP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		DSP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		IF-S	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		GOB	ND	-	-	-							
		PT	ND	-	-								
	Room temperature (5-42°C)	DP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		DSP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		IF-S	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		GOB	ND	-	-	-							
		PT	ND	-	-								
Leaf	Refrigerator (8±1°)	OT	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		DP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		DSP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		IF-S	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		PT	ND	+	+								
	Incubator (28±1°C)	OT	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		DP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		DSP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		IF-S	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		PT	ND	+	+								
	Room temperature (5-42° C)	OT	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		DP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		DSP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		IF-S	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
		PT	ND	+	+								

^a+ = *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* present, - = bacterium absent, ND = test not performed.